

ISic0454

I.Sicily inscription 0454

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates**

37.0767995, 15.2848558

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 261

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Locus Siracusa
2. dd XV k EB Berna
3. cli

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Compare IG 14.172=Agnello, Silloge, n.11= ISic0992 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0992>]

Digital identifiers:

TM 491683

EDCS 21900517

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7176 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650769>)

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